

Key Findings: A review of the policy and economic landscape in rural Scotland: informing plausible scenarios

Fiona Bender, Acacia Marshall, Jonathan Hopkins, Simone Piras
Social, Economic and Geographical Sciences Department, The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen

This piece of work identifies critical drivers of rural change which are described within recent peer-reviewed literature and technical reports. These drivers of change will be evaluated and used to inform the basis of *plausible scenarios* - in other words, likely futures - that could occur in rural areas if these drivers continue to follow current trends. To produce these plausible scenarios, we are using the DEPEST (Demography, Economy, Policy and Governance, Environment, Society and Technology) framework, to draw out relevant themes from the literature. The DEPEST categories of 'macro-trends' affecting places has been applied successfully in rural scenario planning (Piras et al., 2021, drawing on work by Aguilar, 1967) and provides a clear framework and structure for identifying and understanding the major drivers of change affecting rural areas.

This document highlights the key findings that emerged from the DEPEST literature review, which also used evidence from the analysis of the Scottish Islands Survey (2023) (main report: Wilson et al., 2024) and from engagement in living labs in rural Scotland. We summarise a set of 'nexuses of change' (Piras et al., 2021: 960) – topics and questions which are critical for future patterns of economic development in rural Scotland. These are to be further discussed and refined with stakeholders and policymakers, to identify policy-relevant scenarios which can be modelled in the future. The key findings for each DEPEST category are also summarised, below.

Influential drivers of change in the economy of rural Scotland

Nexus of change	Key questions
Demographic processes affecting rural communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can younger people who leave for post-school education and job opportunities – contributing to an aging population – return to live and work in rural areas in greater numbers than previously? • Will migration into rural areas continue at similar rates in the future, both from the rest of the UK (through, for instance, remote working opportunities) and international migration (historically for jobs in key sectors such as health, care and farming)?
Rural housing, transport and infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will the availability and affordability of rural housing improve due to private or public investment?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will rural infrastructure and transport decline and suffer from further cuts, or will they improve and develop as a result of increasing investment?
Climate change and economic benefits from transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will rural places gain long-term place-based economic benefits from the just transition – for example, through wealth and jobs created by renewable energy schemes and rewilding initiatives, and through greater wellbeing? • Will the effects of climate change intensify, impacting rural areas more?
Directions of the tourism sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will less extractive, more sustainable and sensitive models of tourism expand, potentially supported by improved tourist infrastructure and new tourist taxation?
Technological changes affecting working patterns, housing, transport and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can technological changes across society (e.g. improved digital connectivity, online healthcare appointments, electric vehicles) support the needs of rural residents, given an aging population, sparsely populated areas and existing digital divides? • Will rural connectivity improve and become more affordable? • Will the phenomenon of remote working persist and/or expand, benefiting rural, island and remote localities?
Community empowerment and centralization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do all rural places have the human and social capital and capacity to play an active role in community planning and the management of local assets? • Will local authorities and the Scottish and UK Governments – operating at larger scales than rural communities – be sensitive to local needs when designing future policies?
National and international events and crises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic and cost-of-living crisis persist in rural Scotland? • To what extent will additional global events and crises affect the economic and demographic context of rural Scotland? • Will the UK and/or Scotland distance themselves even more from Europe, or start a process of reintegration into the EU?

Key findings: DEPEST categories

Driver 1: Demography

Population trends and characteristics such as age structures, migration trends and the 'push' and 'pull' factors associated with rural areas.

- Rural Scotland has an unbalanced age structure, with an ageing and declining population.
- Outmigration occurs in many rural and island areas and is predominantly seen through young adults leaving their rural area to take up further education and job opportunities that aren't offered in their rural areas.
- Research suggests that more young people are considering returning home, largely due to the high costs of living in urban areas. However, the limited employment opportunities in rural and island areas create a difficult job market.
- Access to greenspaces, nature, the perceived quality of life and the opportunity to work remotely in rural and island areas are attractive options for those who wish to move or return to rural areas.
- The pressure of housing in rural Scotland is increasing as people are purchasing second homes and those at retirement age are moving to rural areas, 'pricing out' young people and those who are looking to move for work.
- Workers for key sectors such as education and healthcare are high in demand. However, in rural and island areas, these occupations often place additional pressure on workers. This may mean individuals seek extra training before taking up the role or the pressure may result in the occupation being off-putting.
- The combination of migration trends and the ageing population can place public services under increasing pressure and impact on community sustainability.

Driver 2: Economy

External factors with impacts on the rural economy including COVID-19 and the EU exit, and local economic characteristics, including income distributions, other inequalities and important industries.

- Part-time work, self-employment and small businesses are more common in rural areas than in urban areas. Those living in the Scottish islands are more likely to work in more than one paid job compared to the rest of Scotland.

- The current shrinking and ageing population is affecting labour markets and efforts to retain and attract workforces are needed.
- Some rural areas are currently seeing a decline in job and educational opportunities. Employment opportunities are harder to access in rural areas and there is difficulty in finding good quality employment opportunities with sufficient pay and progression opportunities for those who return from urban areas.
- There are income inequalities between those living in accessible rural areas compared to those who live in remote rural areas.
- Austerity measures have led to service cuts in rural areas, causing services to become centralised leading to difficulties for rural residents.
- COVID-19 further worsened the labour market and housing challenges, particularly affecting the tourism and hospitality sectors.
- The cost-of-living crisis creates a challenge in the transition to a circular economy. People are more focused on purchasing affordable items from cheaper retailers than making long-term purchases.

Driver 3: Policy and Governance

Government policy and how it relates to rural areas, and governance structures that exist in rural areas.

- Recently, Scottish policy has shifted towards place-based policies, allowing them to better address the unique and specific features of rural areas and community needs. Typologies such as the Gow Typology (Gow, 2023) can be helpful when developing these place-based policies as they can help to differentiate between different types of rural areas.
- Community empowerment is encouraged by the Scottish Government, promoting community ownership and community involvement in risk management. However, a challenge faced by community groups is that the burden can fall on key individuals and groups within the local community and can be dependent on the level of expertise and time they have.
- The prioritisation of rural community well-being is being considered in Scotland through looking into 20-minute neighbourhoods and through the importance of community-led tourism.
- Centralised governance (Scotland or UK) often fails to cater to rural areas and is unable to distribute resources effectively. Local governance, however, struggles to have enough resources to support communities.

Driver 4: Environment

Ecological and sustainability issues, including the role that rural areas play in facing climate change, how resource scarcity could impact on rural areas, and the green technologies that may offer solutions.

- To meet the Scottish Government's net zero by 2045 target, the land management practices which are incentivised (for example, tree-planting and peatland restoration) provide challenges and opportunities for rural areas.
- Rewilding is an activity that can be part of green land investment and while it is a controversial term, it can potentially coexist with re-peopling to revitalise rural areas.
- Renewable energy efforts remain controversial with the challenges of balancing the environment and ecological preservation with the need for sustainable energy.
- The Climate Challenge Fund is an initiative by the Scottish Government that allows support to community climate change initiatives, however the impacts are often limited by community capacities.
- Community connections to land through crofting, cultural heritage projects and community land trusts develop ties to land, creating social capital within communities and improve community wellbeing.
- It is important to address the transport and infrastructure challenges in rural areas (public transport, electric car infrastructure and recycling opportunities) to support the transition to a circular economy.

Driver 5: Society

Cultural aspects of rural areas, how people relate to rural areas in Scotland, and levels of health and mental health amongst rural populations.

- Rural Scotland's current depopulation trend can be largely attributed to young people leaving for education and job opportunities in urban areas, with many not returning.
- Tourism is a key feature of many rural communities. Some view tourism positively: tourists potentially move to rural areas which can strengthen rural communities, bringing new ideas and activism. Challenges also arise, like increased traffic and travel disruption and environmental issues.
- Well-being in rural areas varies, with some studies indicating that rural areas have better well-being due to social cohesion and access to nature while some indicating well-being is worsened due to social isolation.
- Arts and culture are important in rural communities both through supporting business retention and maintaining populations.

- Post-primary educational opportunities are a concern in many rural areas. There is a need to address these challenges to support the provision of education to meet the needs of rural communities and to ensure sustainable community development.

Driver 6: Technology

Exploring the disparities of technological advancement in Scotland, with rural areas often being left behind, and innovations that may change this trend.

- Poor internet connections pose a significant challenge in rural Scotland. Issues such as connectivity speeds and the lack of up-to-date broadband infrastructure are faced in rural areas due to their remoteness and low population density.
- Top-down policy-led approaches seek to address the rural-urban digital divide including broadband connectivity; however, these approaches have been criticised for being overly centralised and for not addressing the specific broadband issues in rural areas. Community-based approaches also seek to improve digital access in rural areas; however, these often require major commitments from rural residents.
- Technological advancements in transport and healthcare offer potential benefits to rural communities, however infrastructure to support these must be addressed first.
- The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the importance of digitalisation and provided the opportunity for remote work, which positively impacted rural employment and resilience.

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Note: References used in the literature review are included in the report “A review of the policy and economic landscape in rural Scotland: informing plausible and aspirational scenarios”.

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